

D5.3 AMON DEC Plan

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D5.3 Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan

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Version	Date	Changes	Changes made by
0.1	31.05.2023	First draft	Adriano Li (FBK)
0.2	04.07.2023	First revision, inclusion of communication activities, tools, and channels.	Ilaria Alberti (FBK)
0.3	25.09.2023	Inputs from partners on dissemination and exploitation activities.	FBK, SE, DTU, VTT, EPFL, ALSW, EFCF
0.4	19.10.2023	Final check	Adriano Li (FBK)

Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Plan (DEC Plan) of the Amon Project. The DEC plan aims to define the materials needed for wide diffusion and an effective communication with the general public, the dissemination activities needed to reach a wide audience of stakeholders and caught the interest of as much public as possible, and the plans, agreements, and activities to secure the proper exploitations of results during and after the ending of the project.

The Consortium will update and refine the plan for the M18 once the project results are clearer and, after the first year of project, the overall design of the system have been defined. At M30 there will be a second update, with more advancement of the results made during the project a more clearer exploitation plan and joint together with the earlier versions. In case major events, changes in the consortium, or redefinitions of results; an update will be made on the DEC Plan to go accordingly with the latest changes.

Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication are an obligation and opportunity for a project to further scale-up the results, shed light on the work done, and bring value to it by creating the chance of a positive impact in various fields and growing the development of knowledge, innovation, and technological readiness level in some cases. These activities if carried well and effectively will bring born to new projects or future research using this project result as a new ground to reach new heights.

01. Introduction

This project deliverable is divided in different sections to carefully evaluate various aspects of the project Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Plan. The plan will first give a background of the framework used to created it, important definitions to understand the context of the plan, and a first estimation of potential activities and result generated during the project with their impact in society. On the second part, it will be described in a more concrete form the planned or estimated activities needed to carry the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan.

These activities are planned to follow the expected results generated during the project and the estimated impact they will when they are exploited. It will also dwell on the "Result Ownership List," a list where for each exploitable result an owner is appointed. This give better clarity of who is the primary beneficiary of the exploitation and who is the one that has a direct responsibility to conduct the mentioned exploitation.

As mentioned before, this document is being written in the first stages of the project. It is still difficult to measure the final form of the result planned to be generated during the project, therefore is even harder to have an exact prediction of the best way to exploited them and the possible impact they will have. For that reason, this document will be updated in M18 and in M30, especially in the latter with a more detailed Exploitation Plan.

02. Background

This document will follow the guidelines given by Horizon Europe in the framework of projects for Research & Innovation. The activities describe in this document are following the proposal made to the granting authority and previously presented to them in the form of a Grant Agreement. The AMON Consortium understand the importance of not just generating new result in Research & Innovation, but also the duty as institutes and organizations with funding from the European Commission to communicate our findings, disseminate the results to a public as wide as possible, and to exploit the result. This means not just to let others know about our research but to find the way to keep progressing the research & innovation in the field either by a commercial way, an academic one, or both.

To achieve our goals, first the definition on keywords is given to give context to the vocabulary used in this document.

02.1 Terminology

To be clear about the content and context of this document, we will be giving a detail definition of the main concepts used, provided by the Regulation (EU) 2021/695 of the European Parliament and of the Council of April 28, 2021.

Define within the framework of the project and the EU regulation:

- **Background:** any data, know how or information whatever its form or nature, tangible or intangible, including any rights such as intellectual property rights, that is: (i) held by beneficiaries prior to their accession to a given action; and (ii) identified by the beneficiaries in a written agreement as needed for implementing the action or for exploiting its results.
- **Communication:** the promotion of the project by giving visibility and providing information to multiple stakeholder groups (including the media and the public). Communication involves using different medias like targeted messages, mediums, and tools. This means to do proper

actions to reach out to society as whole or specific selected audiences (non-specialists) on the topic and its increasing visibility.

- **Confidential/Sensitive Information:** any kind of information share within the Consortium containing knowhow, financial information, personal information of the Consortium, or any information not fit for the public or third parties outside of the Consortium (e.g., contact information of member of the Consortium, financial statements of partners, relevant background of partner institution used during the project, etc.).
- **Copyright:** EU copyright law consists of a range of directives and regulations harmonising essential rights, guaranteeing the protection needed to encourage creativity and stimulate investment in the sector. The aim is to promote cultural diversity and better access for consumers and businesses to digital content and services across Europe. Copyrighting uses licensing as its main mechanism, most often granted directly by the rights-holder or a rights management organisation.
- **Dissemination:** the public disclosure of the results by proper means, other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results, including by scientific publications in any medium.
- **Exploitation:** the use of results in further R&I activities other than those covered by the action concerned, including among other things, commercial exploitation such as developing, creating, manufacturing, and marketing a product or process, creating, and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.
- **Intellectual Property Rights (IPR):** the right to exercise ownership on certain information. The owner of the information can choose how is the information is going to be disclose and how can other, apart from them, can use that information for their own research or commercialization.
- **Public Information:** information available to all others outside of the Consortium. This information can be accessed by anybody does not their origin or affiliation and should be published in platform easy and free of access.
- **Research Output:** the results generated by a given action to which access can be given in the form of scientific publications, data or other engineered results and processes such as software, algorithms, protocols, and electronic notebooks.
- **Result:** any tangible or intangible effect of a given action, such as data, knowhow, or information, whatever its form or nature and whether it can be protected, as well as any rights attached to it, including intellectual property rights.

02.2 Strategic Impact

The overarching goal of AMON project is to develop a novel system for the use and conversion of ammonia into electric power at high efficiency using a solid oxide fuel cell. The project will deal with the design of the basic components of the system including the fuel cell, the ammonia burner, ammonia resistant heat exchangers, the engineering of the whole Balance of Plants, and the validation of the compliance with ammonia use for all the specific parts and components. Optional, to be checked alongside the activities, the ammonia cracker, and an anode gas recirculation. For the development of the solid oxide fuel cell, a G8X cell from SOLYDERA will be utilized, first validated in a laboratory at the level of single cells, for electrochemical properties, degradation, and post-mortem analysis, at the level of single repeating units for the validation of interconnects and sealing components, and at the level of stacks and stack modules. An overall Ammonia fuel cell system will be engineered and manufactured to be assessed in a relevant environment in a port area (Venice). The final system will be in the size of 8

kW stack module, with an ammonia cracker and a heat management system. It will aim at an overall electrical efficiency of about 70%.

As reported in the Grant Agreement, the specific objectives of AMON are to:

SO1	Design and develop a fuel cell stack module at a scale of 8 kWel, tested and qualified to convert (directly or through an integrated ammonia reformer) ammonia into power, possibly using the internal reforming capacity of a solid oxide cell operating at high temperature and managing the power output through the control of the cell fuel utilization. The stack module will be qualified through cell testing (electrochemical, long term and posttest analysis), SRU testing (to qualify interconnecting materials to ammonia), single stack testing (to qualify long term durability, optimization of cell control and fuel utilization, heat balance), and full stack module testing (to qualify and test the specific module operating modes and qualify the stack highest efficiency and specific control strategy).
SO2	Qualify a system 100% tolerant to ammonia in all the components and related materials, including heat exchangers, burner and potential reformers and anode gas recirculation, as well as the fuel cell in all the building materials, layers and interconnects.
SO3	Target 70% system electric efficiency, pursued by the optimal use of the cell to reduce heat generation and consumption and leveraging the fuel utilization to a maximum, integrating novel solutions such as anode gas recirculation to eventually be utilized.
SO4	Validate the stack and system flexibility to allow for 30% partial load and full flexibility in the overall range.
SO5	Qualify the system for at least 3000 hrs operation with demonstrated 90% availability in the operating hours and less than 3% degradation rate at nominal power condition measured over 1000 hours of continuous operation.

In particular, the project aims at achieving the following targets for Solid Oxide Stationary Fuel Cells:

- AMON target CAPEX 5 – 50 kW_e ≤ 5000€/kW for 100 MW of annual production.
- Overall Electrical Efficiency > 70%.
- Availability > 90% in 3000h.
- Degradation < 2.5% per 1000h.
- 100% FC system tolerance to ammonia.
- Dynamic range of operation for 30-100% of nominal load.

The objectives aim at reaching certain impacts, which can be summarised in:

1. Advance the knowledge and scientific proofs for ammonia SOFC.
2. Impact of ammonia as a hydrogen and energy carrier.
3. Use of ammonia in the maritime sector at a full scale.
4. Year-round power generation assuring maximum energy end use demand and reducing thereby the specific CAPEX is reduced.
5. Reduce the barriers on regulation and safety requirements for the use of ammonia.
6. Reaching TARGET END USERS in the industrial sector.

This objective corresponds to specific needs acknowledged by the Consortium, in which we planned expected key result to be achieved in this project to answer them. The key results are measurable outcomes in the project that decide if the aimed objective were achieved or not. These outcomes respond to a need and then are communicated, disseminated, or exploited. In the following table, the specific needs will be presented along with the expected key results and the D&E&C measures to let others know the achievements of this project.

Specific Needs	Expected Key Results	D&E&C Measures
Security of Supply: In response to the recent events, Europe feel the urge to diversify energy supplies and accelerate renewable energy roll-out to replace fossil fuels in homes industries and in	Design and Validation: Proof of concept of novel design SOFC stack module resistant to ammonia fuel. Proof of concept of Novel design Ammonia BOP	Exploitation: a further development to a higher TRL (TRL 3 to TRL 5) of the new system developed within the project to consolidate the technology and eventually propose it to new customers;

<p>power generation.</p> <p>Harbour environments present challenges when it comes to electricity, as they typically are at the end point of the electricity grid and being particularly exposed to strong load changes.</p> <p>Unlock wide markets potential: The opportunity for renewable Ammonia in efficient conversion systems contributes to the decarbonize hard-to-abate- sectors such as maritime autonomous power systems, where volumetric density and long-term storage solution are key requirements. Where other clean alternatives are difficult to implement.</p> <p>Raise industrial interest in ammonia: Components used in the fuel cell system are at prototype phase. With AMON, we can develop new components, validate those components in a relevant environment and bring them at industrial scale. As a perspective, by 2050. The market for ammonia as a fuel for maritime sector and stationary power will be expected to reach 197 Mt. The technology proposed in AMON is capable to address the raised in demand.</p>	<p>components such as: resistant heat exchangers, catalytic burner, (optional) ammonia cracker and (optional) anode gas recirculatory qualified and assessed.</p> <p>Validation of the material exposed at high temperature in a relevant environment. Estimation of the lifetime expected from those materials and components.</p> <p>Successful pilot demonstration:</p> <p>Ammonia fuel cell system at 8 kW SOFC, with high conversion efficiency, long term system durability.</p> <p>Realisation and validation of The AMON integrated system in a relevant environment (Port Venice).</p> <p>Analysis and Guidelines:</p> <p>Safety analysis and technology certification guidelines.</p> <p>Scaled up technology layout with techno economics analysis.</p> <p>Market assessment and specific business case development.</p> <p>Conceptual Design:</p> <p>Development of potential alternatives concepts of more integrated systems.</p> <p>Scientific & Academia:</p> <p>Research results from the validation and modelling of Ammonia SOFC operations and aging. These include cell testing and stack testing.</p>	<p>development of a new ammonia market as a renewable and low-carbon hydrogen and energy carrier. With licensing for R&D and potential commercialization from AL and SolydEra on the AMON system, patenting from AL and DTU for alternative concepts for systems and the other for SOFC concepts, and scientific publications from DTU and SolydEra on the SOFC.</p> <p>Dissemination towards end users, scientific community, and potential clients: organization of a workshop and a final dissemination event involving external stakeholders, participation to relevant conferences, seminars, events, and fairs, scientific publications in high-impact journals and in ORE platform, open access of research data, in line with IPRs, engagement of local educational institutions.</p> <p>Communication towards citizens: public website and social media, graphic and video materials, participation in events organised as part of activities in WP5 targeting the broad public.</p> <p>Communication towards EU and National institutions: to raise the interest on a novel validated solution and to support specific markets growth with proper policy actions.</p> <p>Market assessments and Business case: to identify the specific characteristics and need of the targeted priority market to pivot the technology design and development, the communication strategy, the end user engagement, and the future exploitation actions after the project end. This measure would include the analysis of the business case including all valorisation patterns, whatever direct or indirect, towards the various stakeholders.</p>
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02.3 D&E&C Outcomes

The D&E&C strategy will target audience related to the ammonia sector (production, transportation, storage, end use, trade), especially waterborne transportation, maritime supplying sector and environments, harbours, and off grid applications near to the importing ports. The other group are the fuel cell developers and OEMs as well as SDOs, regulators, and authorities.

These stakeholders are then connected to specific expected outcomes of AMON, as not all outcomes will be of interest or benefit a specific target group. The expected outcomes will then have an expected impact inside of the targeted group or community. To give an overview, the following table is presented:

Target Groups	Expected Outcomes	Expected Impacts
<p>End-user: harbour, maritime environments, waterborne mobility, off-grid applications near to the importing port infrastructure or special fields, where LPG and diesel will be replaced in the future e.g., remote power for ICT facilities. The Port of Venice will host an ammonia import facility.</p> <p>OEMs: other manufacturers can benefit of ready to be used components for expanding the fuel cell system into the market.</p> <p>SDOs, Regulators, and Authorities: by investigating the compliancy issues from the design phase to demonstration, AMON will provide full understanding of any gaps in terms of standards and directive to certify ammonia-fuelled systems.</p> <p>Scientific community: researchers and developers in hydrogen and ammonia related fields</p>	<p>Stakeholders from the supply chain to adapt their products and parts for the transition to Ammonia based fuel cells or expanding of the market to include Ammonia SOFC initiative.</p> <p>End-user to be more motivated to make a change of technology or adoption of Ammonia technology for electric generation in the market.</p> <p>OEMs using the validated components and integrated system to reach higher TRL and bring the technology to the market.</p> <p>New incentive schemes to facilitate the installation of fuel cell systems into the market.</p> <p>Initiate a standardization working group with a Technical Community for standards will help in adopting Ammonia as an energy carrier in fuel cells.</p> <p>Target group stakeholders are convinced of the potential of ammonia as green hydrogen carrier and the fuel cell technology as a reliable and most efficient solution with attractive TCO. They see the steps and timeline of relevant large scale (10-100MW) solutions and will be able to see their role to bring ammonia and the fuel cell solution to success.</p>	<p>Scientific: through modelling and experimental validation, AMON will contribute to the scientific impact of European institution of excellence in the specific sector of SOFC and ammonia operated cells.</p> <p>Economic/Technological: new efficient use of ammonia as hydrogen carrier in a fuel cell system, by skipping an intermediate step (conversion of ammonia to hydrogen)</p> <p>Societal/Economic/Technological: AMON can be the barrier breaker for the acceptance of ammonia fuel cell into the market. It will clarify the system cost and needed safety measures.</p> <p>Industrial: AMON will contribute to the mature of components and systems maturing them for a market application and looking for a production in manufacturing capacity by the industrial players (SolydEra and Alfa Laval), thus bringing to technology depreciation.</p> <p>Standardization: AMON impact the adoption of novel standards in the use of Ammonia as an energy and hydrogen carrier.</p>

03. D&E&C Plan

03.1 Project Identity

As described in D5.2 “Visual Identity,” the visual identity aims to present the project to internal and external stakeholders, it tells a story through the visual communications. The visual identity captures and expresses the values and ambitions of the project, the core activities, and its characteristics. It includes a logo, imagery, typography, colours, and creative design that characterize a project as a distinguishable brand.

The first step of the visual identity is the logo. The logo makes the first impression; thus, it is the first

thing that attracts the attention of users and audience and might spark their interests. It not only helps differentiating AMON from other projects with similar names, but it strengthens the message that the project as in a unique word and graphic symbol the logo embeds the main concepts and meanings of the project. It is indeed characterized by the NH₃ molecule that locates itself on the final part of the

lettering, and the concept is strengthened with the pictogram, which only reports the symbol of the ignition "ON" and the NH₃ molecule.

Besides the shape, colours are another distinguishing feature of a brand identity. The other characterizing element of a logo is the payoff. The final logo is a combination of design, colour, font, and sentence which will be used for all the communication and dissemination material of the project.

Visual identity is the base of templates, e.g., PowerPoints for presentations, Word for reports and documents, and of communication materials such as website, social media, roll-up, flyers, and basic infographics as well as the final brochure and the video.

The visual identity will indeed be the same for the full length of the project.

Communication materials and branding guidelines are available to Partners in the shared drive. This sub-chapter is a brief summary of deliverable 5.2 and 5.4. For more information consult these documents, the first related to visual identity and the second on to communication materials.

What must be underlined is that visual identity is fundamental for the AMON project, and for this D&E&C Plan: using the correct templates and logo will make people immediately recognise that the subject of a presentation or document is AMON Project.

03.2 Stakeholder Groups

Stakeholders are an integral part of all communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities. They are the ones we are focussing our effort to related to and convince the benefits of AMON. But the first thing we have to do before planning an activity is to identify who are the stakeholders and why would they be interested in AMON. To identify who are the stakeholders one needs to understand that a stakeholder can be anyone who has an invested interest or stake on the project. This means that stakeholders come from a wide range of people and from different levels of expertise. They can be the general non-scientific public interested in renewable energy or climate topic to industry experts interested in how the technology is evolving and how to adopt it in their industries.

To get a better understanding of how to relate to the wide range of stakeholders is important to first identify them and then discern what is the most effective channel of communication to attract them to AMON. This will involve the correct use of the communication channels to reach them, use the best strategies for disseminating the results generated during the project, and make it possible for AMON to be exploited to further develop the technology or to make transitions in the industry possible.

Further below we will list the possible stakeholders AMON will interact with.

Industrial Stakeholders:

• System Integrators and OEMs

- Who: Industrial Stakeholders involved in the supply chain for electrochemical reactors, especially SOFC (hot box - unit level), like SOFC OEMs and module/stack provider, balance of plant suppliers, base material suppliers, and manufacturing and test equipment provide.

The supply chain for the comprehensive system i.e., suppliers of Heat exchangers, Burners, Crackers, Tubes, Valves, and Measurement tech/Controller.

System integrators of power modules like (engines, turbines, SOFCs...) into energy supply systems (plant level.) like heat power plants, using gas, oil, waste.

- Technical Knowledge: Advance level of technical knowledge to be used.
- Vocabulary: Use of technical expertise and business proposal vocabulary.
- Means: Presentation in conference, webinars, and commercial negotiations. Booth at trade fairs
- Key Messages: Proof of novel design for Ammonia SOFC system with efficiency of 70% and other alternative concepts for the system, Proof of functional capabilities (reliability, durability, efficiency) including (mass) manufacturability, maintainability, reparability, and future profitability (business case potential, TCO).
- Activities: Hydrogen and Ammonia events and fairs, networking meeting, and workshops, trade fairs, (sustainable) energy events and fairs, power and grid events and fairs
- Type: Dissemination with pitches & (invited) talks, posters, prospects of Exploitation.

• End-Users (Maritime sector and adjacent industries)

- Who: Industry end-users involve in maritime activities (primary maritime applications) and adjacent industries near the maritime activities that can benefit from AMON technology. The focus is particularly on those who are at the end of the electricity grid or do not count with one like ships. This end of the line user tends to have stability problems and can benefit from the use of a clean energy source like the system AMON is developing. this could engineer service provider, industries owners and operators, importers and exporter industries, goods logistics operators, and local authorities.
- Technical Knowledge: Intermediate level of technical Knowledge to be used.
- Vocabulary: Technical vocabulary to prove the advantage of AMON mix with a business vocabulary to remark the economic advantages.
- Means: Presentation in conference and local events/workshops/meetings (in specific ports), webinars, and commercial negotiation.
- Key Messages: Proof of novel design for Ammonia SOFC with efficiency of 70% system and other alternative concepts for the system, short- and long-term advantages and value added.
- Activities: Ammonia events, (sustainable) maritime, green fuel and shipping technology and business-related events, workshops, showcase events, workshops, and networking meetings.
- Type: Dissemination with prospects of Exploitation.

• Investors

- Who: Industry and/or Public Figures or Organizations interested in the commercial or scientific development of clean hydrogen solutions or ammonia for energy solutions.
- Technical Knowledge: Intermediate to low level of technical knowledge to be used.
- Vocabulary: Technical vocabulary to demonstrate the advantage of AMON mix with a business vocabulary to remark the economic advantages and growth potential.
- Means: Presentation in conference, webinars, and commercial negotiation
- Key Messages: Proof of novel design for Ammonia SOFC system with efficiency of 70%, short- and long-term advantages and value added.
- Activities: Clean hydrogen events, ammonia events, maritime business-related events, workshops, showcase events, and networking meetings.

- Type: Dissemination with prospects of Exploitation.

Scientific Community:

• Research Institutes

- Who: Institutes specialized or with potential interest in the research result of the Amon project or clean hydrogen technologies. Participants in parallel or future projects related to AMON content.
- Technical Knowledge: Advanced level of technical knowledge to be used.
- Vocabulary: Advanced technical vocabulary to present and discuss the result and technical achievements of AMON oriented to research and scientific development after AMON.
- Means: Presentation in conference, webinars, poster in events, scientific publications, and videos.
- Key Messages: Research result from the proof of novel design for Ammonia SOFC system with efficiency of 70% and other alternative concepts for the system, development challenges and upcoming hurdles that still need improvements and alternative solutions.
- Activities: Scientific events, showcase events, meeting with institutes of interest, and workshops, discussion groups e.g., within social media.
- Type: Dissemination with prospects of professional Discussion, Collaboration/future Projects, scientific Reputation, and Network

• General Research Public

- Who: Research public from the scientific field with interest in clean hydrogen technologies but no specialized in it.
- Technical Knowledge: Advanced level of technical knowledge to be used.
- Vocabulary: Advanced technical vocabulary to demonstrate the functioning and the importance of AMON pilot and results.
- Means: Presentation in conference, webinars, poster in events, scientific publications, and videos.
- Key Messages: Proof of novel solution potential for Ammonia SOFC system.
- Activities: Scientific events, showcase events, and workshops.
- Type: Dissemination.

SDOs, Regulators, and Authorities:

• Local Authorities

- Who: Local Authorities involved in the policy making of their territory, being it provinces or cities, with a focus on international port cities and regions.
- Technical Knowledge: Basic to intermediate level of knowledge to be used.
- Vocabulary: Basic to intermediate technical vocabulary mix with policy vocabulary in search for political understanding of the AMON technologies and the advantages it can bring.
- Means: Face to face meetings, pilot presentations, and presentation (oral, poster) in specific events
- Key Messages: Advantages of the novel design for Ammonia SOFC system and the benefit it can bring.
- Activities: Showcase events, policy events, visits, webinars, mass mailings, social media.
- Type: Dissemination with prospects of Information, gaining Interest, Exploitation.

• Standardization Bodies

- Who: Technical Community (TC) looking for the revision, modification, or amendment of an ammonia standard in fuel cell
- Technical Knowledge: Highly technical knowledge to convinced group work for any changes in the current standard.
- Vocabulary: Highly technical vocabulary to express the results generated in AMON and to bring in potential changes to standards or being involve in the change of one.

- Means: Meetings, online and face to face discussions, agreements with the TC, and written proposals.
- Key Messages: Admit the results found in AMON in the development of the technology to be part of modification, revision, or amendment of a standard related to fuel cell and ammonia.
- Activities: Submission of proposal to the corresponding stakeholders, contact with strategic stakeholders to open the discussion, and organize meetings with Consortium partners to move forward the initiative.
- Type: Exploitation of results.

General Public:

- **Local News Media:**

- Who: News networks present in the local cities of the partners and the site for the pilot demonstration.
- Technical Knowledge: Basic technical level of knowledge to be used.
- Vocabulary: Basic technical vocabulary with the intention to promote the benefits of the technology and the innovation of it.
- Means: Press release, flyers for information, and interviews, videos, commented pictures.
- Key Messages: Advantages and innovation made for Ammonia SOFC systems and the benefits it can bring, implementation roadmap, breakthroughs.
- Activities: Press release and news articles, web, and social media
- Type: Communication multiplier.

- **NGO**

- Who: Organizations with interest in sustainable energies and clean hydrogen technologies, in particular Ammonia and maritime/ports, if possible.
- Technical Knowledge: Basic to intermediate level of knowledge to be used.
- Vocabulary: Basic to intermediate technical vocabulary.
- Means: Poster in events, videos, flyer communications and face to face meetings, collaboration as media and communication partners
- Key Messages: Demonstration of the benefits (ecologically, economically, operatively, strategically) the AMON technology can bring to ports, cities, and industry. Future potential, implementation roadmap, breakthrough.
- Activities: Sustainable energy events, clean hydrogen events, and workshops, reciprocal info exchange agreements.
- Type: Communication and Dissemination, Partnership.

- **Non-scientific communities**

- Who: Any general public with interest in sustainable energy and clean hydrogen technologies, but no specialized in it.
- Technical Knowledge: Basic level of knowledge to be used.
- Vocabulary: Basic technical vocabulary.
- Means: no extra means, random accessibility via the means used for the other stakeholders Presentations in conference, videos, poster in events, and interactions face to face in events, web, social media.
- Key Messages: Highlight the (sustainable) solution potential (savings, independence, reliability) of the AMON technology and the benefits it brings to their communities and local cities and the general society (Europe, World).
- Activities: Social media posts, sharing of videos, public website, and participation of public events.
- Type: Communication.

03.3 D&E&C Channels

These are the main forms of D&E&C, in which the Consortium will use to inform of the knowledge acquired during the project and the results generated. Most channels conclude in a particular activity that showcase how that channel is use in the project, while other like the AMON website are continuous channels lasting even after the project. It is important to recognize them and have a strategy on how that channels are being used.

Press releases

A press release is a statement format delivered to media for the purpose of providing information, creating an official statement, or making and announcement for public release. In EU projects, press released are done when key activities are completed, or main results are achieved.

The first press release was released in February 2023, following the AMON kick-off meeting, which took place in Trento at the end of January 2023. The document had the aim to inform stakeholders of the beginning of the project. The press release was published through FBK and partners' channels. Then, it was published also on the AMON website. It is possible to read it at this link: <https://amon-project.eu/2023/01/31/amon-project-kicked-off/>. Information on the numbers of visualisation can be found in the report D5.1.

The second press release is expected at the end of the project to highlight the main results achieved and the impact generated. The document will be released immediately after the final dissemination event, when the project results will be presented.

Non-scientific articles: magazines and newspapers

These articles are written on newspapers, online magazines, and non-scientific journals in the field of renewable energy, hydrogen technology, ammonia technology and R&D. The goal of this kind of publications is to periodically inform stakeholders about the project activities and about the most recent results, without going into specific and technical details. Among the targeted magazines, there are the partner's magazines (e.g., FBK Magazine, etc.) and News web page, as well as the dissemination magazines of the EC (e.g., Research*EU Magazine). Other magazines include online journals and blogs in the energy, hydrogen, and ammonia sectors as well as local newspapers. There are several on national and European level. For instance, HydroNews (Italy), H2News, H2Views, Hydrogen Tech World, etc.

In the project at least two articles in online magazine at EU level are foreseen to be published to provide info and update on project activities.

Partners are aware that they must inform the AMON communication manager and provide the link to the article to be shared through the website.

Communication Toolkit

GIFs, flyer, brochure, and templates for poster and presentation are useful tools that help projects to reach a targeted audience with small text and attractive images to communicate information. In this way information can be received faster and in a simpler way with the use of infographics, converting big texts into smaller one with the help of high informative images.

In this project a deliverable will be submitted to specially detail the resource used to cover this channel, the Communication toolkit. The deliverable will include only the first part of tools available, but the Communication toolkit will be continuously updated during the life of the project with new instruments that show the advancement of the project. All tools are based on the unique "brand" for the AMON project with professionally conceptualised and visual identity that is then used in all communication material, which will be used during conferences, fairs, workshops, and events.

The deliverable is foreseen for M12 (D5.4) but will be submitted before (M9) as the communication materials have been designed in the phase of the visual identity conceptualisation. During the second phase of the project, after M18, there will be a future update of the communication toolkit when we have results generated from the project. A video is expected to be realised which should also contain interviews with partners and show the prototype. Also, a final brochure is expected by the end of the

project. The document should summarise the main achievement of the project and give inputs for the exploitation of the results.

Scientific publications

The Consortium targets a minimum of five scientific papers to be published in peer-reviewed journals (“green” open access) Scientific publications are the most relevant format for dissemination of results in the scientific community to contribute to advance the state of the art in the field of solid oxide fuel cell, ammonia technologies, clean hydrogen applications, maritime industry decarbonization, and energy generation.

At this stage of the project, it is still early to have already published articles. However, partners are already starting to plan to publish. The below table shows a list of tentative titles and target journals that partners expect to publish.

List of Planned Scientific Publications						
Date	Tentative Title	Partners	Target Journal	PIDs	License	Status
11.2023	Multiphysics modelling and system analysis of ammonia-fueled SOFC for reliable operation - effects of temperature and ammonia pre-cracking	DTU	International journal of hydrogen energy	Not Published	Green Open Access	Accepted
02.2024	Efficient and Durable System Design for an Ammonia-Fueled Solid Oxide Fuel Cell	DTU	Energy conversion and management	Not Published	Green Open Access	Planned
04.2024	Corrosion and nitriding of steels in an ammonia environment under high operating temperatures	DTU	Chemical Engineering Journal	Not Published	Green Open Access	Planned
04.2024	Study of SOFC-NH ₃ system with respect to NH ₃ precracking	EPFL	To be decided	Not published	Green Open Access	Planned
06.2024	Upscaling approach of SOFC-NH ₃ system	EPFL	To be decided	Not published	Green Open Access	Planned
TBD	8 kW stack performance	VTT	To be decided	Not published	Green Open Access	To be Planned

All scientific publications will be published in open access, following the guidelines for Horizon Europe. Each beneficiary will ensure open access (online access for any user, free of charge) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to results coming from the project activities. The AMON website and the Zenodo Community will serve as a platform to enable open access of the project outputs.

Each partner will:

- Send an electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication to the WP5 leader to be uploaded on the AMON website.
- Upload databases in Zenodo to validate the results associated with each scientific publication.

All publications shall acknowledge the project and the funding. The statement to be included is the following:

This work is part of the research activities of the project AMON. The project is supported by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership and its members Hydrogen Europe and Hydrogen Europe Research, under grant agreement No 101101521.

Presentations and posters at conferences, seminars, and workshops

To share the latest findings within the R&D communities and beyond, the activities and results will be presented and a specific expert workshop for R&D stakeholders, OEMs, suppliers, etc. will be organised at reputed conferences e.g.: European Electrolyser & Fuel Cell Forum (EFCF), ECS Intern. Symposium on SOFC, World Hydrogen Summit & Exhibition, WHTC/WHEC, European Fuel Cell Conference (EFC), online conference/webinars e.g., of Mission Hydrogen.

To address even more industry, investors, policy, and NGOs, the partners of AMON will be actively present and disseminate info material during relevant sectorial events, fairs, seminars, and workshops such as Hannover Fair, FC Expo, Green Hydrogen Forum at The Smarter E (GHF), F-Cell and national events as well as the lighthouse events of Hydrogen Europe and the review days of Clean Hydrogen JU.

To push awareness in the target audience of the ammonia sector incl. the maritime providing sector and potential future application areas and to support the exploitation and market development, AMON will also show up and disseminate info material in the specific ammonia community events, e.g.: NH3 Event Europe, ARENHA events, Ammonia Energy Conference of Ammonia Energy Association (AEA), Argus Clean Ammonia Europe Conference, ICFA International Conference on Fuel Ammonia, IFA Annual fertilizer flagship Conference, European Power to Ammonia Conference, Symposium on Ammonia Energy, Safety in Ammonia Plants and Related Facilities Symposium, etc.

Presentations and posters are dissemination formats used to showcase research results at scientific conferences, seminars, and workshops. Each presentation and poster produce by the Consortium partners will be designed using the visual identity of the AMON project (D5.2). To monitor the impact and visibility of the project, attendance to conference, seminars and workshops will be recorded when needed using the following table.

List of Presentation at conferences, seminars, and workshops.

Dates	Event Name	Type of Event	Activity to be done (e.g., Oral presentation, Poster)	Partners Involved	Place of Event	Status of Activity	Reference
05.2023	First Italian Workshop on Ammonia Energy	Workshop	2 Presentations	FBK, SE	Florence, Italy	Done	https://www.combustion-institute.it/news-events/39-first-italian-workshop-on-ammonia-energy.html
06.2023	NH3 event Europe 2023 - 6th European	Conference	General presentation	ALSW	Rotterdam, Netherlands	Done	https://amon-project.eu/2023/06/14/amon-at-the-nh3-

	Power to Ammonia® Conference						event/
09.2023	European Fuel Cells and Hydrogen Piero Lunghi Conference (EFC23)	Conference	Presentation	FBK	Capri, Italy	Done	https://amon-project.eu/2023/09/25/fbk-presents-amon-at-efc23/
09.2023	Research Night	Public event	Poster	FBK	Trento, Italy	Done	https://amon-project.eu/2023/10/09/amon-at-the-research-night-in-trento/
11.2023	EU Hydrogen Week	Public event	Guest	ALDK	Brussels	Planned	High-Level Policy Conference - European Hydrogen Week (euhydrogenweek.eu)
02-03.2024	21st International Hydrogen & Fuel Cell Expo (World Smart Energy Week)	Fair	Stand (promotion through flyers etc)	VTT	Tokyo Big Sight, Japan	Planned	
05.2024	245th ECS Meeting	Symposium	3D Multiphysics simulation of 8 kWh ammonia fueled SOFC stack	DTU	USA	Planned	
07.2024	EFCF 2024	Conference	<p><i>2 Presentations:</i></p> <p>System design for an 8-kWh ammonia fueled SOFC.</p> <p>Challenges of steel application in direct ammonia</p>	DTU	Switzerland	Planned	

			fueled SOFCs.				
07.2024	EFCF	Conference	Ammonia fueled SOFC system	ALDK	Switzerland	Planned	
07.2024	EFCF 2024 - Sustainable Shipping Days	Workshop		EFCF, ALDK	Switzerland	Planned	
07.2024	EFCF	Conference	SOFC-NH3 system	EPFL	Switzerland	Planned	

Social media presences

In M6, FBK activated two social media profiles.

When the dissemination activities will increase, an editorial plan will be drafted to plan the most efficient way to promote community engagement through regular posting of news, updates, and results.

Nowadays, social medias have a significant impact of how we found out about topics and news. Social media not only works as a form of entertainment but also as a place to learn more about thing we are interested and discover things we were not aware before. That is why social media is one of the communications channels needed to expand the knowledge of result from AMON and the have a bigger impact in society letting know the research and the development is being made to progress the technology, in this case for ammonia fuelled SOFC.

As part of this project, the AMON Consortium will create a LinkedIn dedicated to AMON. LinkedIn being a social media dedicated to business networking where one can find and apply to jobs, and where company or institutes can share accomplishments. The Consortium will also create a Twitter (Now rebranded as "X") for social media interaction varying from the general non-scientific public to experts in different fields and companies using the social media. Twitter serves as an organic growing social media where one can discover content without having to specifically follow other accounts. For example, one can find out about the AMON project by just following other accounts involve in topics of sustainable energy and ammonia.

In both social media there will be periodic posting of content for news, updates, and result. For each social media 1-2 post per month will be made. The content will range from presentations in conferences, when important results are achieved, project meetings being attended, publication of scientific paper, construction of pilot, videos for the technology, etc.

FBK as leader of the communication tools will oversee the social media accounts.

Policy recommendations

One of the most important keys outside research is the political view on clean energy and the transition towards it. Even though each individual institute can develop remarkable results and make big steps towards the progress of clean energy technologies, without the support of the government or local authorities there is a limit to how much things can be changed. At the current speed, the climate is changing, and the global warming occurs, the intervention of policy makers is needed to support the transition to cleaner energies. Therefore, the Consortium have the responsibility to show policy makers the result we are generating and convince them of the feasibility of using technologies, like the ones being develop in AMON, in the industry market while being economically advantageous.

At the end of the project, FBK as project coordinate will organize a final dissemination event will be organized at the AMON installation site. It will include a plant tour, the presentation Key Exploitable Results, policy recommendation, outlook to the next development steps, future market & business cases discussions, networking, and expert & follow-up project talks. At the moment of writing this document, it is too early to predict who will be the persons assisting to the event and how is the event going to be organized.

Audiovisual Resource

At the beginning of the project, two short videos or GIFs were created to show how the prototype should work. The GIFs are available on the Project website.

In the 2nd half of the project, a video showcasing the AMON advancement and technology potential will be made. The purpose of the video will be to target industry and general public. It will be shared via the website, in YouTube, partners communications channels and showed during events if possible.

The video is estimated to be 2-4 min long. At the moment of writing the document it is still too early to predict or planned the structure of the video and what will be shown. It might either show the AMON pilot with partners' interviews or it might be under the form of an animated video. As all the communication materials, partners will be involved in the conceptualisation of the video.

Website

The AMON website (<https://amon-project.eu/>) is an important tool to congregate all the public available information as well as have a more organize and visually pleasant way to showcase information about the technology being develop in the project. The website will be managed by FBK, sharing, and posting information about the progress of the project, animations explaining how the technology works, events where the project is being presented, sharing public results from the project, etc.

It is expected to reach more than 100 visits per week on the website. As of the writing of this document the website is online with description the AMON technology, links to other social media account, news of event where the project was mentioned, and communication tools like the flyer for the project.

Workshops

Beside this, the organization of a focused workshop and/or an "ammonia fuel cell energy" session in collaboration with other projects & innovation activities.

Exploitation workshops (2 internal (HRB) and 1 involving external stakeholders) on characterization of the exploitable results, validation of the business opportunities for key results, identification of the main competitors, identification and assessment of the risks and barriers to be overcome to enable the exploitation of the results, development of a feasible risk mitigation plan, fine-tuning and validation of the EXP Plan and IPR management.

Repositories

Repositories are digital information system to store, manage, preserve, and provide access to digital information. The chosen repository for this project is Zenodo. Zenodo is an open-source digital library, it was built and developed by researchers. CERN, as an OpenAIRE partner and pioneer in open source, open access and open data, provided Zenodo in May 2013. Through Zenodo Big Data management and extended Digital library capabilities for Open data are shared to everyone.

Therefore, Zenodo serves as a digital library to store and shared the results of the AMON with many tools at hand to control the licenses, give PIDs, and form a community around the project. For the duration of the project and after the end of it the Zenodo community for AMON (<https://zenodo.org/communities/amon-clean-hydrogen-ju/>) will be use as repository for databases and results generated.

03.4 Dissemination and Communication Activities

In this section, it is presented a summary of Dissemination and Communication activities with their status. This will be continuously updated and presented in the next update of this document.

Summary of Communication Activities:

Activity	Description	Target	Channel	Impact	Status
Visual identity	Creation of logo, colours, typography, and graphics that make AMON a distinguishable brand	All	Visual identity is the base of all comms materials.	Raise awareness	Completed at M6
Website	Creation of a virtual space where stakeholders are constantly updated through news and results	All	WordPress	Inform and attract	Launched at M6, ongoing
Social Media	Creation of profile in LinkedIn and Twitter to publish the news	All	LinkedIn and Twitter	Engage with stakeholders, gain attention, attract interest, exchange information	Launched at M6, ongoing
Press release and magazine articles	Publication of news on non-scientific journals	All	Partners websites and magazine	Inform, gain attention, attract interest	A first press release was published in Feb 2023. All partners to publish articles.
Communication materials	Creation of materials to disseminate results during events and conferences	All	Roll-up, flyer, templates, GIF, video, brochure	Inform, gain attention, attract interest	Roll-up and flyer ready. Video will start in summer 2024.
Final event	A final event with relevant stakeholders, showcase of the results generated in the Project, site demonstration the technology, and Business Expectation	All	Final event presentation	Inform, gain attention, attract interest, showcase results.	Start to organise it 12 months before the project's end.

Summary of Dissemination Activities:

Name of Activity	Number to Achieve by End of Project	Target Audience	Tools/D&E&C Channels	Partners Involved	Status of Activity
Scientific Publication	5 Publications	Scientific Community	Scientific Publications in Journals Zenodo Repository	DTU, EPFL	1 Accepted (DTU) 2 Planned (DTU) + 2 (EPFL)
Conference Presentation	10 Presentations	General Public Scientific Community Events Participants	Presentations Oral and Posters	ALL	2 Completed (FBK, SE, ALSW)
Webinars	1 Session	Scientific Community	Workshop Audiovisual Tool	To Planned	To be Planned
Website Activity/Visits	100 Visits/week	General Public	Website	FBK	Ongoing
Brochures	> 1000 Copies	General Public Scientific Community Events Participants	Communication Tool Kit	ALL	Ongoing
Flyers	> 500 Copies	General Public Scientific Community Events Participants	Communication Tool Kit	ALL	Ongoing
Social Media Activity	1-2 Post/month	General Public	Social Media Twitter/LinkedIn	FBK	Ongoing
AMON Final Event	1 Final event	Selected Stakeholders	Stakeholder Info Show	ALL	To be Planned

As a final dissemination and networking event, a stakeholder info show* (D5.8, M36) with plant tour, presentations of key exploitable results, business expectation, political aspects and follow-up networking will be organized at the harbour, where the AMON installation is running.

04. Result Ownership List (IPR)

One of the most important things to define is legally who is the owner of each result, especially the key exploitable results, made during the project. Those who have the legal ownership of the result are responsible for the result to be disseminated and exploited. If the ownership of result is not clear in the early phases of the project, the planning for the activities involving those result could be affected therefore the dissemination and exploitation of them as well.

Not having a proper result ownership list (ROL) can negatively affect a project in the mid- and long-term. The possibility of missing key opportunities to disseminate and exploit increase when there is no clear define ownership. It must be emphasised that the opportunities to disseminate and exploit are timebound (e.g., schedule conference, important events, meetings with key stakeholders, etc.). And not having a correctly filled ROL will block the submission of the final periodic report and hence the last payment.

Now to have a clear visualization of who is the owner of what result, Horizon Europe recommends using the ROL, as previously mentioned the Result Ownership List. This tool can help us easily identify who is the owner of each key exploitable result and how can the result be exploited. Consider that this document is being written in the early phases of the project. All exploit activities are an estimation of what is expected to happen, and all of them are subjects of possible changes during the project.

Table for the Result Ownership List						
Key Exploitable Result	Joint Or Single Ownership Result (IPR)	Result Owners (Early Phase Agreement/Not Final Decision)	Other Involved Partners	Owner Country	Will The Owner Exploit the Result?	Does The Exploitation Involves a Third Party?
AMON Integrated System	Joint or Single (to be define)	Alfa Laval Technologies AB (ALSW)	KIWA, SOLYDERA, FBK, SAPIO	Sweden	To be define later in the next project phase	At the moment, it will not. (To be discussed later)
AMON Ammonia-FC Integrated	Joint or Single (to be define)	SOLYDERA	VTT, AL, FBK	Italy	Yes, by licensing for R&D, future commercialization	At the moment, it will not. (To be discussed later)
Approach to Use Direct Ammonia in SOFC	Joint or Single (to be define)	SOLYDERA	DTU, FBK, EPFL	Italy	Yes, by licensing for R&D, future commercialization	At the moment, it will not. (To be discussed later)
Alternative Concepts of more Integrated Systems	Joint or Single (to be define)	Alfa Laval Technologies AB (ALSW)	SOLYDERA, FBK	Sweden	To be define later in the next project phase	At the moment, it will not. (To be discussed later)
Experience & Results of Integrated System Testing	Joint or Single (to be define)	Alfa Laval Technologies AB (ALSW)	SAPIO, VTT, SOLYDERA, FBK	Sweden	To be define later in the next project phase	At the moment, it will not. (To be discussed later)

Research Results of Ammonia SOFC Operation & Aging	Joint or Single (to be define)	SOLYDERA	DTU, EPFL, FBK, VTT	Italy	To be define later in the next project phase	At the moment, it will not. (To be discussed later)
Design of the Control Strategies	Joint or Single (to be define)	Alfa Laval Technologies AB (ALSW)	SOLYDERA, FBK, KIWA	Sweden	To be define later in the next project phase	At the moment, it will not. (To be discussed later)
Alternative Ammonia SOFC Concepts	Joint or Single (to be define)	TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF DENMARK (DTU)	FBK, EPFL, SOLYDERA. AL	Denmark	To be define later in the next project phase	At the moment, it will not. (To be discussed later)
Ammonia cracker	Single	Alfa Laval Technologies AB (ALSW)		Sweden		At the moment, it will not. (To be discussed later)
Heat Exchangers	Single	Alfa Laval Technologies AB (ALSW)		Sweden		At the moment, it will not. (To be discussed later)
Upscaling approach for multi-MW SOFC systems	single	EPFL		Switzerland	Yes, by license	Yes

05. Exploitation

Exploitation, as previously define, is the use of the result generated in this project to further advance the research, development, innovation, and deployment of the technology being built in AMON. This uses can involve the use of the result's data for new research, the surge of new project progressing furthermore the TRL, spread the commercial attractiveness of the technology, or the support of industry transition using the result in AMON.

In AMON, it has been agreed that each partner is responsible to ensure the exploitation of their results. In case a join ownership is agreed, all partners sharing the ownership are responsible for the successful exploitation of results.

To conduct a successful exploitation of results, the ROL is of great importance to determine the responsible and main beneficiary of the exploitation of the result. The next step is to have a clear dissemination strategy and activities to promote the knowledge and result generated in AMON. These steps will culminate in further activities, agreements, or projects using AMON as a new floor for the advancement of the technology.

Currently, as of the writing of this document, is still hard to measure the results and the proper strategy to achieve an effective dissemination and successful exploitation. The D&E&C Plan will be updated later in the project when results are confirmed in the second phase of the project. As of now we can only estimate the possible key exploitable results and a brief description of their potential impact.

The Consortium acknowledges that exploitation is not a recommendation but a duty that has to be achieve. As per the Grant Agreement, if despite a beneficiary partner's best efforts, the results are not exploited within one year after the end of the action, the beneficiaries must (unless otherwise agreed in writing with the granting authority) use the Horizon Results Platform to find interested parties to exploit the results.

In the next table, the Key Exploitable Results (KER) are presented with an estimation of routes for exploitation.

Table of Key Exploitable Results

Name of Result	Result Type	Description of Potential Impact	Expected Time to Generate the Impact	Target Group	How is it going to be Disseminated?	URL or PIDs	Horizon Result Platform?	Key Activity of Exploitation	Market Maturity /TRL
AMON Integrated System	Proof of concept of new product	Set the basis for the development of large power generators in the 100 kW and MW scale for e.g., harbours where ammonia is available as commodity already today. Green ammonia figures as a candidate to become the future standard fuels in maritime applications	To be determine in the next phase of the project	Companies in the autonomous power system, maritime sector	To be Planned	Not possible to know at the moment	No at the moment	Licensing for R&D, Future commercialization	TRL 5
AMON Ammonia FC integrated	Proof of concept of new product	Demonstration of high efficiency, fuel cell-based systems operated on ammonia to provide new options for decarbonization of different energy sectors and facilitate establishing value chains between fuel	To be determine in the next phase of the project	Companies in the autonomous power system, maritime sector	To be Planned	Not possible to know at the moment	No at the moment	Licensing for R&D, Future commercialization	TRL 5

		cell industry and existing players in industrial markets							
Approach to use direct Ammonia in SOFC	Technical Specification	Support EU industry across the whole value chain in the development of the next generation power appliances using ammonia as a fuel.	To be determine in the next phase of the project	Companies in the autonomous power system, maritime sectors, and energy system developers	To be Planned	Not possible to know at the moment	No at the moment	Licensing or direct commercialization by SolydEra	TRL 5
Alternative concepts of more integrated systems	Conceptual Design	New technologies and components to reduce costs and improve flexibility in operation.	To be determine in the next phase of the project	Companies in the autonomous power system, maritime sectors, and complex energy system developers	To be Planned	Not possible to know at the moment	No at the moment	Patenting	TRL 3
Experience & results of integrated system testing	Engineering and Scientific Knowledge	Reduce the barriers on regulation and safety requirements for the use of ammonia	To be determine in the next phase of the project	Companies that will collaborate with the Consortium	To be Planned	Not possible to know at the moment	No at the moment	Consultancy	TRL 5
Research results of Ammonia SOFC	Scientific Knowledge	Increase stakeholders' readiness and acceptance	To be determine in the next phase of the	Academic Community	To be Planned	Not possible to know at the	No at the moment	Scientific Publication	TRL 3

operation & aging			project			moment			
Design of the control strategies	Engineering	Gain and transfer knowledge and experiences to the maritime providing sector	To be determine in the next phase of the project	Engineering & energy system developers	To be Planned	Not possible to know at the moment	No at the moment	Licensing or direct commercialization	TRL 5
Alternative Ammonia SOFC concepts	Conceptual design, Engineering and Scientific Knowledge	<p>Year-round power generation assuring maximum energy end use demand and reducing thereby the specific CAPEX is reduced.</p> <p>Contribute to the decarbonisation of autonomous power systems operated on a liquid carbon-free fuel e.g., digital data transmission sector, such as telecom (5-15 kWe), communication support for critical infrastructures (up to 5 kWe), energy supply (up to 10 kWe) for early warning systems (i.e., hazardous climate-related event transmitters).</p>	To be determine in the next phase of the project	Developers of Ammonia FC systems, Engineering companies, System integrators	To be Planned	Not possible to know at the moment	No at the moment	Scientific publication, Patenting	TRL 3

		These market opportunities represent a suitable steppingstone to deploy fuel cell systems with highly efficient energy conversion rate of ammonia fuel to power within a reasonable timeframe							
Ammonia cracker	Design, prototyping, operation	The cracker will function as a protector of the downstream components including SOFC	To be determine in the next phase of the project.	SOFC system integrator	Via sell of Cracker as component	Not possible to know at the moment	No at the moment	Scientific publication, Patenting	TRL 5

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Art.2

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